

Author Information Sheet

Manuscript Title: Validation of the Sustained Signal Training (SST) Model – Thermogenic Adaptation Without Apparent Recovery Debt

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Conflict of Interest Statement:

The author declares no commercial or financial conflicts of interest.

Funding:

No external funding was received for this study.

Ethical Statement:

This single-subject study was conducted under self-consent with direct data export from FitDays™ and Ōura devices. Devices were used solely for continuity of personal tracking; no manufacturer involvement, validation, or endorsement is implied. Conducted under exempt self-study criteria per 45 CFR 46.104(d)(4) (secondary use of non-identified data); no IRB oversight was required.

Human Subjects: Self-experiment, no external participants.

AI Assistance Statement:

Large-language model tools were used only for editorial assistance (grammar, formatting, clarity). All study design, analysis, interpretation, and conclusions were generated by the author, who retains full responsibility for the content.

Data Availability Statement:

All datasets and supporting materials are publicly available via Zenodo:

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